

CULTURAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF NAKHCHIVAN INTELLECTUALS IN AZERBAIJAN-TURKEY LITERARY RELATIONS DURING THE PERIOD OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract

In this article, the role of Nakhchivan intellectuals in Azerbaijan-Turkey literary relations is determined. As we know, since the end of the 20th century, especially after Azerbaijan regained its independence, the relations between our countries have strengthened, and commendable work has been done in this field. Azerbaijan's mutual cooperation with the Republic of Turkey is a bright example of our country's new relations with foreign countries, the friendship and brotherly relations of a sovereign state with equal rights, and the expression of the new political-economic and national-ideological thinking established in international affairs. Scientists, writers and poets have a special role in the comprehensive development of these relations.

Keywords: Turkey-Azerbaijan relations, Nakhchivan intellectuals, national-spiritual wealth, poet, writer

The history of Azerbaijani-Turkish literary relations began in ancient centuries and continues to develop to this day, enriching both literatures with new creative qualities. These two states, which share a common language, religion, national customs and traditions, historical heroes, and personalities, are connected to each other with unbreakable threads. It is impossible to study the national uniqueness of "one nation, two states" - Azerbaijan and Turkey - in isolation from each other. Despite the seventy-year strict prohibitions and political prohibitions of the Soviet empire, literary relations between Azerbaijan and Turkey have always continued. The changes and new approaches that occurred in socio-political life in the 90s did not bypass literature and literary relations. Over the years, as time changed, the public view of various issues also changed. It became necessary to reconsider a number of issues that were assessed objectively in the post-Soviet space and evaluate them from the point of view of national values. A number of articles and several poetry books have been published in this vein by the poet Khanali Karimli, PhD in Philology, Associate Professor, who has contributed to the development of Azerbaijani-Turkish literary relations. The author has published more than 10 articles on Azerbaijani-Turkish literary relations, both in the country and abroad. Khanali Karimli's book "Ahlat daşı" was published by the "Sam Yayınları" publishing house in Istanbul. Most of the poems in the book are dedicated to the poet's Turkish-Azerbaijani literary relations and the eternal friendship of these peoples. The monograph "Nakhchivan literary environment in the East-West context" presented to the scientific community by the young researcher Nargiz Ismayilova, who is the author of many scientific, artistic and translation works, is a serious scientific research work. The monograph was published by "Akademisiyen kitab evi" in the Republic of Turkey. The author of the preface, academician Isa Habibbeyli, who talks about the content and significance of the monograph, writes: "In the monograph, the East-West traditions in the Nakhchivan literary environment, which began in ancient and medieval times and further developed in the

19th-20th centuries, are extensively studied and generalized. The author theoretically explained and substantiated with artistic examples that the traditions of Eastern literature developed widely in the classical period of the Nakhchivan literary environment" (Habibbeyli I., 2020)

Examples of literary creativity of famous writers living in Nakhchivan, such as Khanali Karimli, Asim Yadigar, Ibrahim Yusufoglu, Elkhan Yurdoglu, Gafar Garib and others, have been published in various publishing houses in Turkey.

Since it is impossible to list all the examples of publications in one article, I would like to draw attention to one issue: the special role of well-known scientists, writers and poets in Turkish-Azerbaijani literary relations, which is reflected in the books and works of various genres published in Turkey by prominent Azerbaijani writers. From this point of view, important tasks also fall on the scientists and writers living in Nakhchivan, which is an integral part of Azerbaijan.

In this sense, the publication of Nakhchivan literature, which has a special place in the Turkish world and the Turkish literary environment and is famous for its artists who have created pearls of art and words, will continue to be very successful in Turkey, and our relations will be further strengthened.

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